

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC-ONLINE CONFERENCE “INNOVATIVE
DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6377320>

Xidirova Dilnoza

*Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan Faculty of Psychology
Philology and foreign languages first year Student*

Abstract: *Research gives birth to innovative teaching strategies and learning experiences. This paper focuses on how research is significant in the field of education and what are different ways by which research and innovation can be promoted in educational institutions. Certain issues like quality, accountability, budget, etc. are discussed in this paper which many colleges and universities are facing today for promoting research. There is a need to foster experiments in the design of new educational programmes. It is very important to replace the old academic activities with a new based on research followed by finding out the effects of these new activities on learning, innovation, and academic achievement.*

Key words: *Innovation and Education, Correlation, Experimental Educational, Quantitative, Mixed Educational researches, Active and Passive methods, Sources of innovative ideas.*

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of innovation into the education system can be seen in the content of education, teaching methods, forms of teaching, types of teaching, teaching aids.

- Innovation in the content of education is explained by the introduction of traditional, non-traditional and distance learning.

- We see the introduction of active, passive and interactive methods of innovation in teaching methods. While the use of the active method serves to increase the activity of students in the classroom, the passive method is explained by giving students a one-sided understanding. The interactive method is understood as active interaction (teacher and student, student with student).

- The introduction of innovation in the form of lessons can be seen in the example of standard, non-standard and virtual forms of lessons.

- Innovation in the types of teaching is explained by problem-based education, heuristic education, tiered education, integrated education, interactive education, informal education, formal education, non-formal education.

Innovation in teaching methods can be seen in the following methods.

1. Active method. This method encourages students to become more active in the classroom, to think about a particular situation or reality.

2. Passive method. This method allows students to develop a one-sided understanding of the topic being studied during the course.

3. Interactive method. The purpose of this method is based on the active interaction of teachers and students in the classroom.

Innovation in the form of lessons can be seen in the following way.

a) Standard lesson - the structure of the lesson does not change.

b) Non-standard lesson - the structure of the lesson changes.

c) Virtual lesson - distance learning. The concept of "new" is central to pedagogical innovation. There is also an interest in private, conditional, local and subjective innovation in pedagogy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An innovation process is a set of innovation cases that replace each other in the process of transitioning the initial state to the final state. The innovation process can be implemented at different levels: federal, regional, municipal, corporate, subdivision. In the field of higher education, the innovation process can be considered as a complex activity associated with the creation, development, use and implementation of new forms of education, effective management mechanisms, new educational products and services. In other words, innovation is the result of the implementation of new ideas and knowledge for the purpose of practical use to meet the specific needs of consumers. Development and introduction of the draft resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On additional measures to further improve the system of retraining and advanced training of teachers in higher education institutions", which provides for the following: Establishment of the Department of Educational Technologies and the introduction of the position of a specialist in international cooperation, with the establishment of a strictly defined (at least 3) teaching staff in the centers for retraining and advanced training of managers and I teachers of universities; Revise the base salaries of staff of centers for retraining and advanced training of managers and teachers of higher education institutions; Higher education institutions retrain managers and teachers training and qualifications introduction of a quality assurance system for improvement processes;

From the information resources of the republican universities, foreign educational and scientific centers for the listeners of the centers creation of conditions for wide use;

Sources of innovative ideas can be:

1) an unexpected event (success or failure, as an impetus for the development or expansion of an activity or the formation of a problem)

2) various inconsistencies (between the real motives of children's behavior, their needs and desires and the practical actions of the teacher);

3) the needs of the pedagogical process (weaknesses of the methodology, the search for new ideas);

4) the emergence of new models of education;

5) demographic factor;

6) changes in children's values and attitudes (changes in children's attitudes to education, important values lead to the search for new forms of communication and professional behavior);

7) new knowledge (new concepts, approaches to education, specific methods and technologies);

8) Peculiarities of innovative activity of the teacher:

9) novelty in setting goals and objectives;

10) deep meaning;

11) the specificity of the application of previously known and the use of new methods in solving pedagogical problems;

12) development of new concepts, content of activities, pedagogical technologies based on the humanization and individualization of the educational process;

13) the ability to consciously change and develop oneself, contributes to the profession.

Five Types of Educational Research

1. Correlational Research a correlational study is a research method where a person may have two or more quantitative variables from similar groups of subjects while trying to ascertain whether there is a relationship between the two variables. Theoretically, he can correlate the two quantitative variables as long as he has scores from similar participants.

2. Experimental Educational Research the major feature that differentiates this research from other types is that the researcher would be able to manipulate independent variables. In this research, there are numbers of design groups for experiments of which some of them qualify as research analysis while others don't. In real experimental research, the researcher would not only manipulate the independent variables but would also randomly assigned individuals to different treatment categories. In quasi-experimental research the researcher would not randomly allocate subjects to control groups and treatments, i.e., the treatment would not be distributed among the participants randomly.

3. Quantitative Research quantitative educational research is a research method that emphasizes statistical, measurement, and numerical analysis of collected data through surveys, polls, and questionnaires by manipulating pre-existing statistical information based on computational techniques. The primary objective of conducting this research is for determining the relationship between one thing and another within a population. The study research design is either in narrative or experimental form.

4. Qualitative Research a qualitative educational research is an exploratory research study that is used in gaining an understanding of underlying reasons, motivations, and opinions. The study research offers insights into the problem or assists in developing ideas or hypothesis for future quantitative research. This research study

can also be used in uncovering trends in opinions and thoughts and digs deeper into the problem. Furthermore, the research method varies by use of unstructured and semi-structured techniques. Also, it is used in quantifying the problem by generating data which can be transformed into real statics. The research uses measurable data in formulating facts and uncovering patterns in research. The data collection method of quantitative research is more structured than qualitative ones. This research method includes different forms of surveys, e.g., online, mobile, paper and kiosk surveys. Others include face to face, telephone interviews, online polls, website interceptors, and longitudinal studies

5. Mixed Educational Research the mixed research method involves the mixing of qualitative and quantitative data, paradigms, process, and methodology in study analysis or set of studies related. This research is a particular case of multimethod study. The research can be improved through the use of multiple methodologies, standpoints methods, data, and perspectives. There are three classes of this research study they include the quantitative design approach, qualitative design approach, and interactive status layout. The quantitative research study is a study at its core with both qualitative and quantitative method added to improve it by providing wider and fuller answers to questions asked, while qualitative study helps in improving the research study by providing larger and fuller answers to research questions.

Tasks of the department of scientific research, innovations and training of scientific and pedagogical staff:

- Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Laws, Presidential Decrees, Orders, Resolutions, Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, Decisions of the Board of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, orders, letters of recommendation, modemograms and telephone messages, as well as rector's orders in faculties, departments, divisions ensure implementation and monitoring;
- General management of all activities and staff of the department;
- Development of work plans of the department and ensuring their implementation;
- Coordinate the activities of the responsible departments of the educational institution based on the objectives of the department;
- To inform students about the content of decrees and resolutions adopted by the President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Enterprise, organization;

CONCLUSION

There are a number of other pressing issues for universities to innovate and improve the quality of education. In particular, the introduction of innovations in higher education is often slowed down from the point of view of teachers due to the excessive workload of their teaching hours and the lack of financial incentives. The new system of teacher incentives does not satisfy many of them. It is therefore necessary to

address the issue of decent salaries for teachers, as in this case it is difficult to require them to fully implement their efforts and significantly increase the level of pedagogical skills. Finally, it is important to keep abreast of changes in the university system. Such an analysis can be carried out in a variety of ways, one of which may be to study the public opinion of the main subjects of the higher education system - students and teachers. It is important that they evaluate the progress of innovations because they are ultimately focused on them and it is up to them to make these innovations a reality. Comparing the calculations obtained allows us to talk about the problems that arise in universities, their prospects, and more. After all, it is difficult to hope for a successful outcome of the transformation of higher education if teachers and students do not support the proposed innovations.

REFERENCE:

[1]Ambalova S.A. Shaxs va uning ijtimoiy dunyoga kirishi // Ilmiy tadqiqotning azimuti: pedagogika va psixologiya. 2016. T. 5.No 1 (14). S. 9-11.

[2]Bekoeva M.I. Falsafiy, psixologik va pedagogik jihatlarda shaxsning o'zini o'zi anglash qobiliyatini shakllantirish muammosi // Tolyatti davlat universiteti fanlari vektori. Seriya: Pedagogika, Psixologiya. 2015. No 1. S. 25-28.

[3]Boykin, L. (1972). Why Research in Education? Educational Leadership. Retrieved from

[4]Taxoxov B.A. Zamonaviy universitetning o'quv jarayoni sifatini boshqarish // Kosta Levanovich Xetagurov nomidagi Shimoliy Osetiya davlat universitetining xabarnomasi. 2014. No 4. S. 283-287.

[5]Yasmeen, S. (2015, April). 22 Extraordinary Education Innovators. Education World.